

COLONIALISM AND ITS IMPACT ON MALEK BENNABI AND THE REASONS BEHIND ITS SUCCESS IN THIRD-WORLD COUNTRIES FROM HIS POINT OF VIEW

AHMAD HAMED IBRAHEEM ALQUDAH

Professor, Modern and Contemporary History, Department of History, Faculty of Arts, Ajloun National University. Email: ah.alqudah@anu.edu.jo

MOHAMMED SALEM AMAYREH

Department of History, Faculty of Arts, Ajloun National University. Email: dr.amyerh@yahoo.com

Abstract

This research sheds light on the impact of colonialism on the life of the Algerian Arab intellectual Malek Bennabi, who experienced colonialism as a child when he was a student in Algeria. Also, later as a university student and engineer in France. He considered colonialism the greatest danger ever brought by humanity against itself. Bennabi attributed the success of colonialism in the Third World countries to the ignorance that was dominant over them and the tactics used by colonialism, such as destroying social networks, fighting intellectuals and thinkers, employing traitors, and the failure of the United Nations in fulfilling its role in maintaining global peace and security, and the idea of colonial vulnerability with in the colonized peoples' societies. The research used a historical analytical approach to examine Malek Bennabi's views on colonialism through his books.

Keywords: Malek Bennabi, Algeria, Colonialism, United Nations, Colonial Vulnerability.

INTRODUCTION

The Arab countries suffered from Western colonialism, with Algeria at the forefront, which was occupied in 1830 by France. France used policies of killing, displacement, and ignorance against the Algerian people. Among them was the Algerian Arab thinker Malek Bennabi, who experienced colonialism as a child when he was a student in Algeria, and later as a university student and engineer in France.

This research aims to shed light on colonialism from the perspective of the Arab thinker Malek Bennabi and its impact on his thoughts and life, especially since he suffered from its **cruelty**. Therefore, Bennabi's view was that colonialism is the greatest danger humanity has ever inflicted upon itself, and that the notion spread by colonialism—claiming it came to save backward and incapable peoples—is false. Colonialism strips the colonized of their civilization, reducing them to a state of degradation to maintain control over them.

Bennabi attributed the success of colonialism in Third World countries to the ignorance that dominated over these countries, the advancement of the West, and the tactics employed by colonialism, such as destroying social networks, fighting intellectuals and thinkers who would play a role in the development of their nations by spreading awareness, as well as the emergence of collaborators (employing traitors) who are considered more dangerous than colonialism itself.

He also pointed out the failure of the United Nations to fulfill its role in maintaining global peace and security. Additionally, Bennabi highlighted the colonial vulnerability of colonized peoples to colonization, which forms the basis of his colonial theory. He argued that there are two factors contributing to the emergence of colonialism: the colonizer, who stands against any attempts at progress by the colonized country, and the colonized, who accept humiliation and colonization, failing to resist by building their civilization but instead idolizing the civilization of the colonizer. Thus, colonialism is seen as a result, not a cause.

The research is based on a historical analytical approach to Malek Bennabi's views on colonialism through his books, including *Conditions of Renaissance*, *Civilizational Struggle in Colonized Countries*, *Journals of Malek Bennabi*, *In the thick of the Battle*, and others. Additionally, some references discussing Bennabi's ideas, such as *Problems of Civilization* by Zaki Milad and *Malek Bennabi as a Reformist Thinker* by Asaad Al-Sahmarani, were also consulted.

Malek Bennabi, His Life and Works

Malek Bennabi was born in Constantine, Algeria, in 1905 to poor parents. His father, Omar, worked as a guard in the government administration in Tébessa, while his mother, Zohira, worked as a tailor to provide for the family's needs **(Al-Abda, 2006, p. 22; Al-Ba'athi, Vol. 2, 1985, p. 197)**.

He experienced the taste of deprivation at the age of six, when his father was unemployed for a period in Tébessa. As a result, his older uncle took him in to raise him in Constantine. Unfortunately, his uncle soon passed away, and his uncle's wife returned him to his parents. Malek recalls this period in his diaries: "My parents were without a source of income and without work in Tébessa for a long time.

This was a very difficult time for my family. My older uncle in Constantine, who had taken me in for a long time, passed away, and his wife returned me to my parents in Tébessa." **(Malik, 1984, p. 18)**.

He was then enrolled in a traditional Qur'anic school and continued his education there, even while attending a French school **(Al-Abda, 2006, p. 23)**. He did not abandon Islamic culture despite attending the French school, and he frequently visited the mosque **(Al-Qurayshi, 1983, p. 32)**.

He lived in Tébessa until 1918, where he completed his preparatory studies. Due to his academic excellence, he was awarded a scholarship to continue his secondary education in Constantine **(Al-Sahmarani, 1984, p. 14)**. Not long after finishing his secondary studies, he entered the workplace, working as a clerk in the Aflo court **(Al-Khatib, 1993, p. 35)**. He then transferred to the Châteaudun court but resigned **(Al-Sahmarani, 1984, p. 15)** due to the mistreatment of the employees.

Bennabi decided to pursue higher education in Paris, where he aspired to study law. He applied to the Institute of Oriental Studies **(Malik, 1970, p. 27)** but was not accepted. He explains the reason for his rejection, saying, "It is not based on academic standards for an Algerian Muslim, but rather on political ones. **(Malik, 1970, p. 27,29)** " Later, he

enrolled in a wireless telecommunication school to study electrical engineering after being advised by his friend, Bournié. **(Malik, 1970, p. 29-30)**

In France, he met a French woman in 1931 who later became his wife. She converted to Islam because of him and took the name Khadija. She influenced various aspects of his life, particularly through the questions she asked him about Islam and the Quran, or her views on comparing Islam and Christianity. He says, "In her own way, she sometimes benefited me, or drew my attention to things that remain significant for someone who does not underestimate the value of simplicity." **(Malik, 1970, p. 106-107).**

After settling in Paris for a period of time, Malek Bennabi established a network of relationships that quickly expanded and diversified. He connected with Moroccan, Tunisian, and Algerian students, gathering them in a special center where he engaged in intellectual, political, and reformative awareness activities. This led to him being referred to as the "Leader of Moroccan Unity. **(Malik, 1970, p. 59).**" His student connections were not limited to these groups, however; he also built bridges between himself and students from colonial territories such as China and French Indochina. **(Malik, 1970, p. 112).**

In 1935, Malek Bennabi completed his studies and graduated as an electrical engineer. During this period, he was anticipating traveling to the East, particularly to the Hejaz or Egypt, where he hoped to continue his studies at Al-Azhar University **(Milad, 1998, p. 45).** However, his application to enter Egypt was rejected because he was known for his anti-colonial attitude. He recounts in his journals: "I immediately went to the Egyptian embassy, where the ambassador at the time was Fakhri Pasha.

When I reached the door and entered, I felt as though I had set foot on the land of my Arab or Islamic homeland, or both together... At that time, the Egyptian consul received me, and when I arrived, I saw the two passports on his desk: "You want to travel to Egypt..." I left the consul's office, and as I stood on the sidewalk, I turned around to read the sign on the embassy door: 'Embassy of the Egyptian Kingdom.' What a deception! I was deceived by it when I was with Farid Zayn, a member of the secret association for Arab unity." **(Malik, 1970, p. 210-213)**

The French authorities began to tighten their grip on Malek Bennabi due to his political activities. In 1938/1939, they prevented him from continuing his teaching at the Adult Literacy Institute for Algerian workers in France, claiming that he lacked the necessary qualifications **(Malik, 1981, p. 119).** After this experience, he headed to Tébessa, but he could not stay there due to the hardships caused by World War II. He returned to France with his wife in 1939. Reflecting on this, he stated: "I felt that there was nothing left for me in Tébessa, so I decided to return with my wife on September 22, 1939... " **(Malik, 1970, p213)** His return to France had a psychological impact on him, and he expressed his feelings about it by saying: "O land of ungratefulness! You feed the foreigner... and leave your own children to hunger. I will not return to you... unless you become free!" **(Malik, 1970, p214)**

In France, Malek Bennabi began defending the cause of his homeland, Algeria, as well as the broader Islamic Ummah, through publishing newspapers and books. He stayed in

France until 1956, when he moved to Egypt and never returned to France **(Milad, 1998, p. 46)**. Zaki Milad explains the reasons behind his migration to Egypt as follows: **(Milad, 1998, pp. 46-47)**

1. His admiration for the personality of Jamal Abdel Nasser.
2. His support for the political initiative represented by the Bandung Conference of 1955, which he considered a pathway to liberation and independence for the Third World from imperialist control.
3. The rising tide of the popular revolution inside Algeria, with Cairo serving as the center for its leadership.

In Cairo, Malek Bennabi began contributing to the defense of his country's cause by publishing his message "Help... The Algerian People are being subjected to genocide. **(Al-Qurayshi, 1983, p. 40)**" During this period, he attracted many Arab and Muslim students and intellectuals, including Abdel Sabour Shahin **(Al-Haras, 1993, p. 16)**, who translated many of his books into Arabic **(Al-Haras, 1993, p. 16)**. He also established connections with numerous Egyptian intellectuals and scholars, such as Ihsan Abdel Quddous, Sheikh Nasser Ibrahim Al-Saleh, Omar Meskawi, and Abdel Rahim Tarif, a professor at the Islamic Law in Beirut **(Al-Haras, 1993, p. 16)**. He also contacted President Jamal Abdel Nasser, and the Egyptian government allocated a monthly salary to him, which helped him dedicate more time to his intellectual work ⁽¹⁾. Cairo became, for him, a window through which he looked to the East. From there, he moved towards Syria and Lebanon, visiting them in 1959 and engaging with their cultural and intellectual circles **(Al-Qurayshi, 1983, p. 41)**

After the independence of Algeria, Malek Bennabi returned to his homeland in 1963, where he took on the position of President of the Algerian University. He later became a counsellor for higher education and the General Administrator of Higher Education. However, he resigned from his position in 1967 to focus on intellectual and reformist work, due to pressure from certain movements opposed to his Islamic ideas **(Al-Ba'athi, 1985, p. 227)**. He held a weekly seminar in Algiers, which attracted youth from across the Maghreb (the western part of the Arab world) and Europe. This weekly seminar took place at his home on 50 Franklin Roosevelt Street **(Al-Ba'athi, 1985, p. 227)**. Malek Bennabi passed away in late 1973 while crossing the Algerian desert on a cultural mission. At that time, he was 68 years old **(Al-Qurayshi, 1983, p. 40)**.

The impact of colonialism on the life of Malek Bennabi

The French colonization of Algeria is considered the driving force behind Malek Bennabi's feelings and thoughts to defend the cause of his country, Algeria ⁽²⁾. Since his childhood, he has heard and witnessed the displacement of his people from their cities and villages **(Al-Idrisi, 1993, p. 10)**. He was also sensitive to the devastating changes that the French imposed on the lives of the Algerian people, such as the spreading of poverty and ignorance, the destruction of social and economic balances, and the consolidation of inequalities between European settlers and the indigenous population. ⁽³⁾

Malek, as an Algerian who tasted the bitterness of colonization and lived a harsh life under its shadow, says: 'My father remained for a long time without any source of income....'(Malik, 1970, p. 18). Also, when he tried to find a job in Tebessa after finishing his secondary studies as a contractor in the roads and bridges department, he couldn't, because the French monopolized this type of work. (Malik, 1970, p. 28) Furthermore, his rejection from the Institute of Oriental Studies to study law was not something he saw as subject to academic standards, but rather to political criteria (Malik, 1970, p.27). These two incidents left a scar in his heart, which he expressed in his journals by saying, 'Today, after forty years, I see clearly that the two men—the humble manager of the roads department in Tebessa and the respected director of the Institute of Oriental Studies—were speaking the same language—the language of colonialism. This deprived me of becoming a contractor... and that deprived me of opening a law office...' (Malik, 1970, pp. 28- 29).

Thus, during his time in Paris, Algeria was never far from his reformist and nationalist thoughts. He began openly expressing his opposition to colonialism (Malik, 1970, pp. 40-41). In Paris, he formed friendships with the people of other colonies, such as China and India, at the wireless school, and he established a movement against colonialism that was formed within the school. He was the frontman of this opposition. Malek states that he was the leader of this front, without a title. (Malik, 1970, pp. 112).

When the colonial circles sensed his intellectual brilliance and his firm belief in resisting colonialism, they sought to limit his activities in Paris through:

First: Monitoring his activities, restricting him, and attempting to kill him. '...to the policy of restriction and strangulation, and they may eventually resort to murder. Colonialism followed this plan with Malek Bennabi... (Al-Jundi, 1965, p. 67).

Second: Transferring his father to another job in a remote area in the Algerian desert. Nevertheless, Malek continued to resist colonialism, saying: 'I was affected by these hardships that started to ensue in my family because of me, without changing my behavior because of them. On the contrary, the events themselves made me more stubborn and rebellious in the eyes of the colonial administration, which, in that very month, February 1923, began to focus on student circles after an event took place in the capital of Algeria, where the governor ordered the prohibition of any activity by the Association of Ulama in the mosques of the country.' (Malik, 1970, p62-63).

Third: Preventing him from conducting the necessary practical training required for every engineer after graduating from the engineering college. Abdelrahman Al-Tamhazi says: 'He was surprised, after graduation, by something he hadn't expected. He was surprised to find the doors closed before him, as he couldn't do the necessary training for every newly graduated engineer, because colonialism had recognized the mentality that Malek carried, and he never stopped connecting with the events of the Arab world and responding to them (Al-Jundi, 1965, p. 67).

Fourth: Preventing him from teaching at the school for illiterate Algerian workers in France, claiming that he didn't have the necessary qualifications to teach the alphabet... **(Malik, 1981, p. 119).**

As a result of the colonial policy against him, he returned to his homeland, Algeria, in 1938/1939, but he could not stay there due to the difficult living conditions caused by World War II. He returned to France with his wife in 1939. His return to France had a psychological impact on him, and he expressed this state by saying: 'O ungrateful land! ... You feed the foreigner... and leave your children to hunger. I will not return to you... unless you become free!' **(Malik, 1970, p. 314).** Indeed, Malek did not return to his country until it gained independence, specifically in 1963.

Colonialism also had an impact on his intellectual life and political activity. He said: 'The only harm that colonialism inflicted on me, which hindered my activity, came through a religious Islamic institution or authority in an Arab country (Malik, 1986, p. 174). He addressed the issue of colonialism in most of his writings after having lived through it first as a child and student in Algeria, then as a student and engineer in France, and later in Egypt, while he struggled against it. Through newspapers and book publications, he issued in 1949 his book *The Conditions for Renaissance*, which tackles the problem of civilization and revival in the Islamic world **(Al-Jabri, 1990, p. 139)**. He also wrote *Labbaik* and *The Afro-Asian Idea in Light of the Bandung Conference*, which was held in Indonesia in 1955. He published several articles in Algerian and French newspapers, such as *the Republic* and *El Shab El Muslim*. He stayed in France until 1956, when he left for Egypt and never returned to France again **(Milad, 1998, p. 46)**. Malek considered colonialism, from a historical perspective, a setback in human history, with its origins dating back to Rome, which left its colonial mark on the historical record. Malek denies this label from the Islamic conquests, which he viewed as a new type of experience in the history of relations between nations. Islamic rule did not colonize in the materialistic, degrading sense of the term, but rather, its conquests of lands such as southern France, Spain, and North Africa were not for exploitation, but to incorporate them into Islamic civilization, similar to Syria or Iraq **(Malik, 1986, p. 148)**. He believes that colonialism has two forms, which are:

- 1. The Protective Colonialism:** This type does not directly interfere in all aspects of the colonized people's lives, but grants them some degree of freedom **(Malik, 1986, p. 108)**.
- 2. Authoritarian Colonialism:** This type directly intervenes in all aspects of life, including religious matters **(Malik, 1986, p. 108)**.

Malek explained that regardless of its form, colonialism aims to control countries and impoverish them by plundering their wealth and exploiting their resources. 'Colonialism did not attempt to achieve a harmonious investment of the colonized countries, where labor was enslaved and servitude aimed at enriching the colonizer more than providing for the colonized **(Malik, 1979, pp. 19-20)**. This is contrary to what the colonizer claims, that the reason for colonization lies in the supposed savagery of the colonized countries

and their lack of civilization (**Malik, 1981, pp. 40-41**). Malek believes that colonialism was based on the myth of the "chosen race" and the disdain for other races, which led to the emergence of the notion of a "superior race" among all human races (**Malik, 1986, p. 124**). He clarifies that the reason for the emergence of this view lies in the fact that:

- The colonial administration was no longer a public administration or an entity of the state, but gradually became an "individuals' company" or, more accurately, it became a "gang" of companies (**Malik, 1986, p. 125**).
- The European individual became disconnected from humanity, isolated from it, driven by his desire for control and colonization (**Malik, 1986, pp. 41-42**). "He particularly believes that history and civilization begin with Athens, pass through Rome, then suddenly disappear for a thousand years, only to reappear in Paris during the Renaissance. As for what came before Athens, there is nothing worth mentioning in the mind of this individual, filled with pride... who sees nothing between Aristotle and Descartes but emptiness. (**Malik, 1981, p. 161**).

Malik believes that the goal of the colonizer is domination, expansion, and the oppression of people, not the civilizing mission or the protection of "inferior" people, as the colonizers would justify. He says, "It is colonization. Yes, it has torn open our door, shaken our house, and robbed us of precious things... It has taken our freedom, sovereignty, and dignity, our forgotten books, the jewels of our thrones, and the soft cushions on which we wished we could have remained asleep" (**Malik, 1986, p. 149**).

The Causes of Colonialism's Success According to Malik bin Nabi in Third World Countries: Malik believes that the success of colonialism is primarily due to the colonizer's thorough study of the Third World from all political, economic, social, intellectual, and psychological aspects before colonization. This allowed the colonizer to identify the weakness points and exploit them for their own purposes. As Malik says, "Like guided missiles, it strikes wherever it pleases. We cannot imagine how much it deceives us to make us mere trumpets through which it speaks and pens with which it writes. It exploits us and our pens for its own aims, using both our actions and ignorance." (**Malik, 1986, pp. 155**)

The spread of ignorance in Third World countries, according to Malik, is the root cause of the catastrophe and colonization of the region. He states, "The general Islamic thought in the twentieth century is flawed in its metrics. We tend to overestimate the outcomes of major causes and underestimate, or even neglect, the impact of minor causes." (**Malik, 1995, p. 109**).

The colonizer worked to create sectarian and religious conflicts within the colonized countries to keep them under control. Social relationships, or social unity, are what ensure a society's survival and preserve its identity. They organize their vital energy, enabling it to perform its collective historical actions. (**Malik, 1986, p. 76**). Therefore, the colonizer uses all means to destroy this network of social relationships, even if those means are as harsh as "the sting of a needle at the right spot, which causes paralysis in the social network of a colonized country" (**Malik, 1986, p. 78**).

Realizing that wars are not won through material weapons alone, such as rifles, cannons, or even airplanes (**Malik, 1986, p. 151**). The colonizer works to prevent the people from reforming themselves. He creates systems for corruption and destruction (**Akasha, 1986, p. 47**). "Just as the colonizer put in place the arrangements to impoverish the colonized materially, he follows them with measures to corrupt their morals, deepening both poverty and moral decay, thus widening the gap to prevent the colonized from ever reaching maturity. " (**Malik, 1976, p. 44**)

Malik emphasizes that corrupting the state's systems is more dangerous than military invasion. He comments on this by saying: "The destruction of the state apparatus is worse than a military attack because it allows for the silent and obscure erosion of the state's apparatus until it collapses into pieces, without our ears hearing anything of what is happening, nor our eyes seeing anything of this work. This process will not end before the body of society has eroded, its springs destroyed, and its joints disappeared. However, the element causing the disease in this field—the destroyer—belongs to two categories: the acute ('viral') type and the 'inactive' type. The acute viral destroyer is one who works through his relationships with other groups of his kind, consciously aware of his goals: he knows he is destroying society, the state, and the system..." (**Malik, 1995, p. 111**). Malik attributes the success of colonialism in the Third World to the prevalence of traitors who play a role in paving the way for the colonizer by providing information about the general conditions of the country before its colonization. Malik comments on this by saying: "In order for imperialism to know our weaknesses—and sometimes to increase their number—it certainly has, in every Third World country, a network of informants who can, if necessary, turn into executing agents. Otherwise, imperialism is like a child that we carry on our backs." (**Malik, 1995, p. 28**).

The role of the traitors does not end with the departure of colonialism; it continues, and they play a dangerous role. Malik comments on this by saying: "We would be even more naive if we thought that colonialism leaves behind only, at times, remnants in places like Vietnam and Congo... it doesn't always leave all of this behind... but always, without exception, it leaves behind the fifth column, the column of its former servants, or as Boumediene said, the column of the *Harkis (the active people)*. Here begins and repeats the tragedy of the country from which colonialism has apparently departed, for the remnants of this colonialism do not simply remain as a pile to be erased by the passage of time... We would be truly naive if we thought that this pile left in the abandoned place would quickly return to become an organized whole, shaped by an organized will that never loses its direction. It will once again become an octopus with many limbs, with local legs and a head thinking from abroad." (**Malik, 1995, pp. 56-57**)

The failure of the United Nations to fulfill its role in maintaining security and peace, despite the hope that it would perform this task effectively, is highlighted by Malik. He says: "Something called the 'global conscience' sought to come into existence and presented its credentials, namely the 'United Nations Charter' and the Declaration of Human Rights. However, the democratic spirit that oversaw the drafting of these historical documents was democratic only in name, as it forgot, in its formulation, to address the issue of the

people. Thus, its attention shifted to states, and in the process, it completely forgot to mention anything about the human being, who had been placed in abnormal situation by colonialism, represented in the children of the colonies" (**Malik, 1981, pp. 120-121**). This "global conscience," which remained silent when necessary, finds nothing to say regarding certain internal issues, as described by colonialism in its discourse on matters concerning colonized countries. Thus, the colonized country, according to this assumption, became an "internal affair" in which the high conscience, namely the United Nations, does not intervene (**Malik, 1976, p. 121**). These results astonish Malik, but Gary al-Touba responds to his astonishment and surprise by saying: "I don't understand how Malik expects the United Nations to abolish the old colonial system! How can he expect this when we have a similar experience in the League of Nations? Isn't the United Nations, like its predecessor, the League of Nations, an institution of Western civilization that emerged to defend its own existence? And which people gained their freedom and independence through the United Nations before paying the price of independence, soaked in blood, with numerous victims on their land and the peaks of their mountains...?" (**al-Touba, 1977, p. 67**).

I say to Malik, what has the United Nations done in the case of Palestine? I tell him that the United Nations has become incapable of defending itself, as it is under surveillance. So, how can we expect someone who does not possess their freedom to grant freedom to others?

Colonial vulnerability is a term introduced by Malik Bennabi in 1948 in his book *The Conditions for Renaissance*. It generally refers to the civilizational decline that affected Muslims in recent centuries, which enabled their enemies to overcome them, colonize them, and impose their civilization. This means there is a certain social disorder, negligence in fulfilling duties, and a lack of knowledge and understanding in the face of the colonial deception and cunning, which allows the invader to conquer a large country with a small number of soldiers. The illusion of the enemy's overwhelming strength leads to acquiescence and acceptance. This backward situation is what facilitates the control of the invaders (**Al-Abda, 2006, p. 80**). Malik Bennabi expressed this idea by saying: "Colonialism is not the result of the notions or actions of politicians, but rather it stems from the very soul that accepts the humiliation of colonization and allows it to take root in its land. Liberation from colonialism can only be achieved by freeing the soul from the vulnerability to it." Malik believes that the responsibility for colonial vulnerability lies with the people themselves, not with the colonizers. He says: "There is one disease that afflicts Arab people everywhere, in the Maghreb (the western part of the Arab world) and the Middle East, for centuries. That disease is the loss of self-confidence, and the traits that have tainted our morals, such as backstabbing, slander, idolizing titles, and flattery of leaders..." (**Malik, 1986, p. 137**). This vulnerability reflects on the overall life of the colonized nation, which has lost the meaning of civilization, particularly in the cultural aspect, which is part of the nation's heritage. Malik says: "We live in a world still tainted by the sin of colonialism, facing those obsessed with a 'culture of domination' who do not want to give the newly liberated people from colonial conquest the opportunity to implement a 'cultural program'... There are films, records, magazines of immoral content,

and books on sex education... But in addition to this external danger, there is another danger coming from within ourselves... **(Malik, 1984, p. 137).**"This vulnerability also takes root in all aspects of life and remains to this day. Malik says: "The European style suddenly infiltrated the trumpet, the pine tree, the telephone, and the car in various Islamic countries fifty years ago, but the problems of backwardness remained deeply entrenched in these countries. Instead of taking on the task of building a civilization, we sought to merely accumulate its products. **(Malik, 1982, p. 62).** " However, vulnerability to colonization is not a chronic disease; it is merely a stage that any society that has suffered from colonialism goes through, and it can be overcome through the collective efforts and energies of the people. There must be the following tasks to be undertaken: **(Al-Sahmarani, 1984, p. 175; see also, Al-Hilali, 1968, pp. 32-35).**

- Reactivating the Islamic spirit in practical life and establishing a collective system committed to this spirit.
- A cultural revolution aimed at focusing on truth, with its elements being ethics, work, industry, and jihad.
- Defining the goals of political independence through liberation, to be complemented by a process of cultural and economic development.

These are the factors of colonialism's success, according to Malik, who considered it one of the most dangerous things that humanity has brought upon itself, because even though it leaves the colonized lands, its effects remain. He says, "It is a phenomenon that characterizes colonized countries. In any country where the flag of independence was raised, did it not face an immediate crisis that erupted at the level of its leadership? It is as if every nation in the Third World is standing at the edge of independence. " **(Malik, 1986, p. 26).** Malik also notes that colonialism itself does not leave the country until it has set its foundations on fire, which he refers to as "decolonization." He says, "This method, followed by the British in Palestine, is more evident. The withdrawal of the British army came with the field left to the Zionists, who had been prepared and united by their leadership to play their role. Meanwhile, the Arab leadership flooded their people with lavish speeches, tearing their unity apart. Instead of focusing on the salvation of the nation, each one sought to seize a part of it." **(Malik, 1986, p. 27).**

Malik Bennabi believes that getting rid of colonialism is not achieved simply by expelling the armies and declaring a day of independence or national holiday, nor by assigning a committee of lawyers to draft a constitution for the country. True independence, he asserts, is the decolonization of the mind before anything else. He says, "Indeed, when a person works for independence and the elimination of colonialism, they face an urgent necessity, which is the decolonization of the mind before anything else. The decolonization of the mind requires many things, including the concepts of solidarity and civilization. It is not achieved merely by the withdrawal of colonial armies, the declaration of independence, or the drafting of a constitution, as is the case with the land of the nation. " **(Malik, 1986, p. 29).**

CONCLUSION

The study concluded with a set of results:

1. Malik Bennabi is considered an Arab thinker who dedicated himself and his writings to researching the problems facing the Islamic nation, attempting to find solutions for them. This is evident in his books *The Conditions for Renaissance*, *Reflections, For Change*, and *The Face of the Islamic World*.
2. The dominant theme in Malik Bennabi's thought is construction, not destruction. He seeks to move from a bad reality to a better one, meaning he attempts to uplift the Islamic society. This is evident in his approach to the problem of colonialism, where he identifies its causes and effects, ultimately calling for its elimination.
3. Colonialism, in Malik Bennabi's view, is one of the most dangerous things that humanity has ever inflicted upon itself because it aims to destroy the colonized peoples economically, politically, intellectually, and socially, rather than uplifting them, as colonialism claims.
4. The success of colonialism in Third World countries is due to the widespread ignorance within them, contrasted with the advancement of the West, and the lack of confidence in the Third World's ability to confront colonialism.
5. Getting rid of the vulnerability to colonialism is not achieved by the departure of the colonizer, nor by declaring a constitution and human rights. Rather, it involves the decolonization of minds and souls, unity, and the ability to create a civilization rather than just accumulate the civilization of others.

Footnotes

- 1) He also received assistance from his friends. Abdul Salam Al-Haras says: "One of the most interesting things to be told here is that when we wanted to print the book *Conditions of Renaissance*, Malek had only forty Egyptian pounds left from his allowance, which was a donation from his friend, the engineer Saleh bin Al-Sa'i." (Al-Haras, 1993, p. 17).
- 2) The impact of colonialism reflected on many Algerian intellectuals and thinkers such as: Mufdi Zakaria, Sheikh Bachir El-Ibrahimi, Mohamed El-Dhib, Malek Haddad, and Ahmed El-Tayeb Ma'ash, who worked to confront colonialism just like Malek Bennabi. See: (Al-Zubairi, 1968, p. 33 and beyond)
- 3) For more details on the colonial policy in Algeria, see:(Al-Asali, 1980, p. 159 and beyond)

References

- 1) Idrissi, Ali (1993): The Social and Cultural Influences in the Formation of Malik Bennabi's Personality, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia: Al-Faisal Magazine, Issue 96, April.
- 2) Al-Baathi, Ibrahim (1985): Contemporary Islamic Personalities, Vol. 2, Cairo: Al-Sha'ab.
- 3) Bennabi, Malik (1984): Journals of a Witness to the Century – The Child, Translated by Marwan Al Qannawati, Dar Al-Fikr: Damascus.
- 4) Bennabi, Malik (1982): Algerian Horizons, Translated by Tayeb Cherif, Algeria: Al-Nahda Library.
- 5) Bennabi, Malik (1979): The Muslim in the World of Economics, Damascus: Dar Al-Fikr.

- 6) Bennabi, Malik (1986): *Between rightness and Confusion*, Damascus: Dar Al-Fikr.
- 7) Bennabi, Malik (1986): *Reflections*, Damascus: Dar Al-Fikr.
- 8) Bennabi, Malik (1986): *The Conditions for Renaissance*, Translated by Omar Masqawi and Abdel Sabour Shaheen, Damascus: Dar Al-Fikr.
- 9) Bennabi, Malik (1981): *The Afro-Asian Idea in Light of the Bandung Conference*, Damascus: Dar Al-Fikr.
- 10) Bennabi, Malik (1981): *In the thick of the Battle*, Translated by Omar Masqawi, Damascus: Dar Al-Fikr.
- 11) Bennabi, Malik (1970): *Journals of a Witness to the Century, The Student*, Translated by the Author, Beirut: Dar Al-Fikr.
- 12) Bennabi, Malik (1984): *The Problem of Culture*, Translated by Abdel Sabour Shaheen, Damascus: Dar Al-Fikr.
- 13) Bennabi, Malik (1995): *For Change*, Damascus: Dar Al-Fikr.
- 14) Bennabi, Malik (1986): *The Birth of a Society, Social Relations Network*, Translated by Abdel Sabour Shaheen, Vol. 1, Damascus: Dar Al-Fikr.
- 15) Bennabi, Malik (1986): *The Face of the Islamic World*, Translated by Abdel Sabour Shaheen, Damascus: Dar Al-Fikr.
- 16) Al-Touba, Ghazi (1977): *Contemporary Islamic Thought, Study and Evaluation*, Beirut: Dar Al-Qalam.
- 17) Al-Jabri, Muhammad Saleh (1990): *Cultural Communication Between Algeria and Tunisia*, Beirut: Dar Al-Gharb Al-Islami.
- 18) Al-Jundi, Anwar (1965): *Contemporary Thought and Culture in North Africa*, Cairo: Al-Dar Al-Qawmiya for Printing and Publishing.
- 19) Al-Khatib, Suleiman (1993): *The Philosophy of Civilization in Malik Bennabi's Thought*, Beirut: The University Press for Studies.
- 20) Al-Zubairi, Al-Arabi (1968): *Algerian Intellectuals and the Revolution*, Algeria: National Museum for the Mujahid.
- 21) Al-Sahmarani, As'ad (1984): *Malik Bennabi, A Reformist Thinker*, Beirut: Dar Al-Nafa'is.
- 22) Al-Abda, Muhammad (2006): *Malik Bennabi, Social Thinker and Reformist Leader 1327-1393H / 1905-1973*, Damascus: Dar Al-Qalam.
- 23) Al-Asali, Bassam (1980): *The Algerian Resistance to French Colonialism*, Beirut: Dar Al-Nafa'is.
- 24) Akasha, Shaif (1986): *Civilizational Conflict in the Islamic World, An Analytical Study in the Philosophy of Civilization in Malik Bennabi's Thought*, Damascus: Dar Al-Fikr.
- 25) Al-Qureshi, Ali (1983): *Social Change in Malik Bennabi's Thought*, Cairo: Al-Zahra for Arab Media.
- 26) Milad, Zaki (1988): *Malik Bennabi and the Problems of Civilization*, Damascus: Dar Al-Fikr.
- 27) Al-Haras, Abdul Salam (1993): *My Memories with Malik Bennabi in Egypt, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia: Al-Faisal Magazine, Issue 196, April*.
- 28) Al-Hilali, Ahmed Aqeel (1968): *New Colonialism and the Responsibilities of Revolutionary Forces*, Damascus: Al-Insha'a Press.